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Role Of Cancer Biomarkers In Diagnosis & Predicting The Future

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Abstract

Introduction

Cancer diagnosis is critical in selecting optimal treatment modalities and improving patient outcomes. Tumor markers are often detected in blood samples and aid in the diagnosis and monitoring of many forms of cancer e.g. alpha-fetoprotein (AFP), carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA), and carbohydrate antigen 19-9 (CA 19-9) etc(1). Elevated AFP levels suggest the existence of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and certain germ cell cancers, making it valuable for early identification, treatment response assessment, and prognosis prediction. CEA is a tumor marker that is typically increased in colorectal, lung, breast, and pancreatic cancer. CEA levels can be used to identify cancer recurrence, assess therapy response, and predict prognosis. Combining CEA with other diagnostic modalities is frequently used to improve its diagnostic accuracy. CA 19-9 is predominantly linked to pancreatic cancer, and increased levels are found in the vast majority of people with this disease. CA 19-9 assists in the diagnosis, staging, and follow up of pancreatic carcinoma.

Aim & Objective

This study was planned to assess diagnostic role of CA 19.9, CEA and AFP in Pancreatic, Colorectal, and Hepatocellular Carcinoma respectively and to compare their levels with age and sex matched healthy controls.

Materials & Methods

The present study was conducted at Dharmshila Narayana Superspeciality Hospital in Delhi's Department of Pathology. Twenty-five individuals each with Pancreatic, Colorectal, and Hepatocellular Carcinoma respectively were enrolled in the research. Routine biochemical examinations were performed on serum samples taken from these individuals along with specialised testing. CA 19.9, CEA and AFP levels were estimated in Pancreatic, Colorectal, and Hepatocellular Carcinoma patients respectively and also in respective healthy controls by Immuno-metric immune-assay method.

Results

Mean CA 19.9 levels were elevated and highly significantly in pancreatic cancer patients (n=25) as compared to age and sex matched healthy controls (<0.001). Mean CEA levels were also significantly higher in colorectal carcinoma patients (p=0.043) as compared to age and sex matched healthy controls (n=25). Mean AFP Levels were significantly raised in hepatocellular carcinoma patients (n=25) as compared to age and sex matched healthy controls (p=0.007).

Conclusion: These indicators should be analyzed in combination with other diagnostic procedures and clinical evaluation to guarantee their proper usage. To improve the accuracy of cancer diagnosis and monitoring, future research efforts should focus on the creation of more sensitive and specific tumor markers (2).

Introduction

Cancer is a complicated illness characterised by the uncontrolled development and spread of aberrant cells throughout the body. Cancer develops when genetic changes such as transcription, mutations, or post-translational modifications etc. interrupt the normal cell growth and renewal process(3). Cancer diagnosis is critical in selecting optimal treatment modalities and improving patient outcomes. Discovery of prostate-specific antigen in prostate cancer screening has motivated researchers to identify suitable markers for screening different types of cancer. Biomarkers are useful not only for diagnosis but also for monitoring disease progression, predicting disease recurrence and therapeutic treatment efficacy. With the advent of new and improved genomic and proteomic technologies it is now possible to develop biomarkers that are able to reliably and accurately predict cancer outcomes.

Recently efficient screening programs with tumor markers have led to an increased number of early cancers diagnoses as asymptomatic malignancies, or in some instances even as premalignant lesions. The definitive diagnosis of cancer has, however, relied on histological evaluation of tissues. An ideal tumor marker would be a protein or protein fragment that can be easily detected in the patient's blood or urine, but not detected in a healthy person(4). Tumor biomarkers are important in cancer evaluation in a variety of clinical contexts. They can aid in risk assessment, distinguishing benign from malignant Tumors, predicting prognosis, monitoring disease state, and evaluating therapy response in metastatic situations(5). In the future, discovery of newer

biomarkers may predict tumor outcome in advance and predict the response of individual tumors to particular therapeutic drugs may be developed (6).

Dr Joseph Gold in 1965 recognized a substance in the blood of patients with colon cancer that was normally found in fetal tissues and named it carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA). Additional biomarkers developed in the 1980s were CA 19-9 for colorectal and pancreatic cancer, CA 15-3 for breast cancer and CA-125 for ovarian cancer. However, these early markers have proven to be unreliable indicators of early disease as they are present in basal levels in normal individuals and are substantially higher only when there is a considerable amount of cancer present. Furthermore, these markers are for the most part not specific for a single cancer. For example, patients with lung or breast cancer can often have elevated CEA, and CA-125 can be high in women with noncancerous gynecological conditions. The future of cancer management is expected to be profoundly dependent upon the use of biomarkers that will guide physicians at every step of disease management. Cancer biomarkers can be used for the accurate evaluation and management of the disease in different stages. They can be useful for predicting several outcomes during the course of disease including early detection, outcome prediction and detection of disease recurrence. Most importantly, with the clinical appearance of many new therapeutic agents, appropriate markers can be used to determine which tumors will respond to which treatments in order to predict the likelihood of drug resistance (7).

Globally, pancreatic cancer is the fifth most common cause of death contributing approx. 85% by pancreatic exocrine adenocarcinoma while pancreatic endocrine cancers are quite uncommon. Compared to women, men are somewhat more affected. CA 19-9 is predominantly linked to pancreatic cancer, and increased levels are found in the vast majority of people with this disease. CA 19-9 assists in the diagnosis, staging, and follow up of pancreatic carcinoma. However, it's important to note that elevated CA19-9 levels are not specific to pancreatic cancer and can also be seen in other conditions, such as liver disease, biliary obstruction, and other cancers. Thus, due to its low sensitivity and specificity, its utility as a screening tool is restricted (8). The reason for elevated CA19-9 levels in pancreatic cancer is not completely understood, but it is believed to be related to the production and shedding of CA19-9 by pancreatic cancer cells. CA19-9 is a glycoprotein, and its levels can be elevated in the blood when it is released into circulation from cancer cells. The exact mechanism is not fully elucidated, but it is thought that pancreatic cancer cells may produce and release CA19-9 into the bloodstream. It's also worth mentioning that not all individuals with pancreatic cancer will have elevated CA19-9 levels, and some individuals with other conditions may have elevated CA19-9 without having pancreatic cancer (9).

The slow and quiet spread of pancreatic cancer is infamous for causing late-stage diagnosis. It is difficult to treat due to its innate resistance to chemotherapy and radiation as well as a propensity for early metastasis. Only 37% of patients with localized pancreatic carcinoma survive, compared to just 12% and 3% of patients with regional and distant metastases, respectively. Individuals with both resectable and incurable gastrointestinal and

hepatobiliary malignancies should pay close attention to the CA 19-9 biomarker. The risk of an early recurrence is indicated by elevated pre-operative CA 19-9 levels, which helps surgeons make better treatment choices. In non-resectable cancers with unclear margins, assessing the residual mass after chemotherapy or radiation therapy becomes more difficult (10). Changes in CA 19.9 levels in these circumstances provide insightful information regarding the Tumor's response to therapy. Before therapy, a greater CA 19-9 level is typically indicative of a bad prognosis.

Hepato-cellular carcinoma (HCC) accounts for approximately 700,000 deaths globally each year. Viral hepatitis, chronic liver disease, and liver cirrhosis are the most prevalent causes. Although curative therapies for early-stage HCC have improved significantly, alternatives for late-stage patients, which regrettably make up the majority and have a dismal prognosis, remain restricted. It is critical to diagnose hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) early in order to improve patient outcomes. High levels of alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) have been identified as a risk factor for HCC development and may assist identify at-risk people. However, utilizing AFP as a stand-alone indicator to screen the general population for HCC has sparked debate. Elevated AFP levels can also occur in non-cancerous liver diseases, decreasing its usefulness as a standalone screening tool. Furthermore, the frequency of HCC in the general populace is modest, and AFP has a low positive predictive value (PPV), making it inappropriate for identifying persons at high risk of HCC in this environment (11).

The fetal liver and yolk sac produce alpha-fetoprotein (AFP), a glycoprotein with a molecular weight of 70 kD, during the first trimester of pregnancy. The fetal analogue of serum albumin, it was originally identified in human fetal serum in 1956, and its lack in adult serum led to its discovery and labeling as AFP (12). AFP levels drop sharply after delivery and stay low the rest of one's life. In mature humans, the precise cellular role of AFP is yet unclear. Serum AFP concentrations in healthy individuals normally range from 5 to 10 ng/mL. High-risk individuals can use AFP levels over 400 ng/mL as a diagnostic tool to rule out HCC. AFP concentrations below 100 ng/mL, however, are less accurate since individuals with chronic hepatitis might show somewhat raised AFP levels. Surprisingly, normal AFP levels are seen in roughly 40% of HCC patients. Although low survival rates in HCC have been associated with high AFP, it is still unclear if HCC with normal AFP production is a unique or aberrant form of the illness (13).

Several researchers reported cancer biomarkers have been found to have low sensitivity in that they are found only in a small subset of patients with a particular type of cancer. Although these markers are not useful for general screening, they can be useful in detecting recurrent disease in those patients whose tumors produce that particular marker. One such biomarker is CEA, which is present in a subset of ovarian cancers (14).

The complex oncofetal marker carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) is a glycoprotein that contains around 60% carbohydrates. It was discovered in 1965 by Gold and Freedman and comes from the stomach, pancreas, and liver embryonic tissues(14). Since CEA levels are high in colorectal Tumors, it serves a crucial function as an inter-cellular adhesion molecule. By encouraging the survival of Tumor cells and enhancing Tumor

angiogenesis, CEA has an impact on cancers. Preoperative CEA levels are important markers for surgical planning and staging in patients with colorectal cancer. A worse prognosis is linked to elevated preoperative CEA levels. Additionally, CEA is employed to keep tabs on individuals receiving systemic medication, particularly in the case of metastatic colorectal cancer. As a result, despite their unsuitability for disease screening, blood CEA levels are used to keep a check on cancer recurrence post-surgery (15).

The reason for elevated CEA levels in colorectal cancer is thought to be related to the production and release of CEA by cancer cells. CEA is a glycoprotein, and it is produced during fetal development. While its role in normal adult tissues is limited, it can be reactivated in certain cancers, including colorectal cancer. Once in the bloodstream, CEA can be detected in blood tests. The release of CEA into the bloodstream may be due to factors such as increased production by cancer cells, shedding of CEA from the tumor, or impaired clearance from the blood (16). CEA is also elevated in endometriosis and some other benign conditions and fails to identify more than 50% of the early cancers, thus it is not recommended for use in a general screening. However, in patients whose primary tumor is CEA positive, post-surgical elevation of CEA levels reflect recurrent disease. Also, CEA, which has low specificity and insufficient sensitivity to be used as a screening marker but is useful in follow-up (17).

Aim & Objective

This study was planned to assess diagnostic role of CA 19.9, CEA and AFP in Pancreatic, Colorectal, and Hepatocellular Carcinoma respectively and to compare their levels with age and sex matched healthy controls.

Material and Methods

The present study was conducted at Dharmshila Narayana Superspeciality Hospital in Delhi's Department of Pathology. Twenty-five individuals each with Pancreatic, Colorectal, and Hepatocellular Carcinoma respectively were enrolled in the research. A 6 mL venous blood sample in a simple vacutainer was obtained under aseptic circumstances from both diagnosed patients and healthy volunteers for the investigation. These samples were processed within thirty minutes after being collected. The serum was separated by centrifugation (2000 rpm X 10 min) after clotting and examined the same day. Routine biochemical examinations and a full hemogram were performed on serum samples taken from these individuals as part of the analysis.

CA 19.9 levels, CEA levels and AFP levels were estimated by Immuno-metric immune-assay method (18)(19)(20).

Principle:

Biotinylated antibody binds to the antigen present in the sample. Streptavidin captures this antigen-antibody combination in the wells. Following that, all unbound pieces are eliminated using a washing method. The immobilized antigen is then bound by a horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-labeled antibody conjugate, which is also a mouse monoclonal antibody against the antigen. Any unattached components are rinsed away once more. A luminous reaction is used to measure the bound HRP conjugate. A reagent containing luminogenic substrates (a luminol derivative and a peracid salt) and an electron transfer agent is applied to the wells. The connected conjugate's HRP catalyzes the oxidation of the luminol derivative, resulting in light production. A substituted acetanilide acts as an electron transfer agent, increasing the quantity of light generated and extending its emission. The light signals are read by the system, and the quantity of HRP conjugate bound is proportional to the concentration of antigen present in serum.

Normal Values in serum CA $19.9 \leq 37.0$ U/mL, CEA ≤ 3.00 ng/mL and AFP ≤ 7.22 IU/mL (21) (22).

Statistical Analysis of data: The data was compiled and analyzed using IBM SPSS statistics version 20 and appropriate statistical procedures. Mean \pm Standard Deviation (Mean \pm SD) was used to express continuous variables. The continuous variables were analyzed using an independent t-test. $p < 0.05$ is considered significant, $p < 0.001$ considered highly significant and $p > 0.05$ considered as non-significant. Furthermore, the charts and graphs were presented using IBM SPSS Statistics version 2.0 and Microsoft Excel 2010.

Results

The present study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at Dharmshila Narayana Superspeciality Hospital, Delhi. A total of 25 newly diagnosed patients of each Pancreatic, Colorectal and Hepatocellular Carcinoma respectively were enrolled in this study. The blood samples were drawn at the time of diagnosis (Pre-treatment).

The following observations were made:

Table 1: Age distribution of Pancreatic carcinoma patients and healthy controls

	Controls (n=25)	Cases (n=25)	P Value
Mean ± SD	54.68 ± 13.08 years	59.76 ± 9.54 years	0.124
Range	32 – 78 years	40 – 78 years	

Table 1 shows that average age of pancreatic carcinoma patients at the time of diagnosis, was mean ± SD = 59.76 ± 9.54 years and ranged between the age of 40 – 78 years as compared to healthy controls with mean ± SD = 54.68 ± 13.08 years and ranged between 32 – 78 years. This difference was found to be statistically insignificant with p-value of <0. 124. Hence age was comparable between pancreatic carcinoma patients and healthy controls.

Table 2: Age distribution of Colorectal carcinoma patients and healthy controls

	Controls (n=25)	Cases (n=25)	P Value
Mean ± SD	58.72 ± 14.67 years	64.80 ± 13.55 years	0.317
Range	30 – 80 years	25 – 83 years	

Table 2 shows that mean age of the colorectal carcinoma patients at the time of diagnosis was mean ± SD = 64.80 ± 13.55 years and ranged between the age of 25 – 83 years as compared to healthy controls with mean ± SD = 58.72 ± 14.67 years and ranged between 30 – 80 years. This difference was found to be statistically insignificant with p-value of <0.317. Hence age was comparable between colorectal carcinoma patients and healthy controls.

Table 3: Age distribution of Hepatocellular carcinoma patients and healthy controls

	Controls (n=25)	Cases (n=25)	P Value
Mean ± SD	40.36 ± 20.92 years	41.20 ± 21.04 years	0.888
Range	16 – 86 years	16 – 87 years	

Table 3 shows that mean age of the hepatocellular carcinoma patients at the time of diagnosis was mean ± SD = 41.20 ± 21.04 years and ranged between the age of 16-87 years as compared to healthy controls with mean ± SD = 40.36 ± 20.92 years and ranged between 16– 86 years. This difference was found to be statistically insignificant with p-value of <0.888. Hence age was comparable between colorectal carcinoma patients and healthy controls.

Table 4: Mean CA 19.9 (U/mL) levels in Pancreatic carcinoma patients and healthy controls

	Controls (n=25)	Cases (n=25)	P Value
Mean ± SD	13.68 ± 10.67	3799.22 ± 4860.09	<0.001
Range	1.40 – 34.50	35.90 – 17400	

Table 4 shows that mean CA 19.9 levels were found to be higher in pancreatic carcinoma patients with mean ± SD = 3799.22 ± 4860.09 U/mL as compared to healthy controls with mean ± SD = 13.68 ± 10.67 U/mL . This difference was found to be statistically highly significant with p-value of <0.001.

Figure 2: Shows mean CA 19.9 levels in Pancreatic carcinoma patients and healthy controls.

Table 5: Mean CEA (ng/mL) levels in Colorectal carcinoma patients and healthy controls

	Controls (n=25)	Cases (n=25)	P Value
Mean ± SD	1.718 ± 0.69	150.32 ± 357.08	0.043
Range	0.37 – 2.81	3.310 – 1330	

Table 5 shows that mean CEA levels were higher in colorectal carcinoma patients with mean ± SD = 150.32 ± 357.08 ng/mL, as compared to healthy controls with mean ± SD = 1.718 ± 0.69 ng/mL. This difference was found to be statistically significant with p-value of 0.043.

Figure 3: Shows mean CEA levels in Colorectal carcinoma patients and healthy controls.

Table 6: Mean AFP levels in Hepatocellular carcinoma patients and healthy controls

	Controls (n=25)	Cases (n=25)	P Value
Mean ± SD	2.70 ± 1.26	112.39 ± 193.09	0.007
Range	0.74 – 5.53	7.31 – 682	

Table 6 shows that mean AFP Levels were higher in hepatocellular carcinoma patients with mean ± SD = 112.39 ± 193.09 IU/mL, as compared to healthy controls with mean ± SD = 2.70 ± 1.26 IU/mL. This difference was found to be statistically significant with p-value of 0.007.

Figure 4: Shows mean AFP levels in Hepatocellular carcinoma patients and healthy controls.

Discussion

Cancer biomarkers are laboratory tests used to supplement the diagnostic process, not the primary approach for detecting cancer. Serum or tissue tumor markers have been proposed for use in clinical practice to predict prognosis, monitor therapy response, and aid in recurrence detection. Nonetheless, several of these markers are not sensitive or specific enough to differentiate between benign and malignant versions of the disease.

This study included 25 cases of each pancreatic, colorectal, or hepatocellular carcinoma respectively who had just been diagnosed. When the patient was diagnosed, blood samples were taken. Patients with pancreatic cancer had an average age of 59.76 ± 9.54 years at the time of diagnosis, ranging from 40 to 78 years. The average age of healthy controls was 54.68 ± 13.08 years, with a range of 32 to 78 years (as shown in Table 1). The mean age at diagnosis for colorectal cancer patients was 64.80 ± 13.55 years, ranging from 25 to 83 years. The average age of the healthy controls was 58.72 ± 14.67 years, with a range of 30 to 80 years (as shown in Table 2). The average age at diagnosis for patients with hepatocellular carcinoma was 41.20 ± 21.04 years, ranging from 16 to 87 years, while healthy controls had an average age of 40.36 ± 20.92 years, ranging from 16 to 86 years (as shown in Table 3).

The study found that mean CA 19.9 levels in pancreatic cancer patients were significantly higher, with a mean standard deviation (SD) of 3799.22 ± 4860.09 U/mL, compared to healthy controls, who had a mean SD of 13.68 ± 10.67 U/mL. This discrepancy was regarded statistically significant with a p-value of 0.001 (as seen in Table 4 and Figure 2).

The threshold value for CA 19.9 in our study was chosen at 37 U/mL.

The usefulness of pre-operative serum CA 19-9 levels to predict pancreatic cancer stage and determine resectability has been extensively studied. Kim et al. evaluated CA 19-9 serum levels in 114 pancreatic cancer patients who underwent either pancreatic resection (N = 72) or palliative bypass surgery (N = 42). These authors reported a positive correlation between pancreatic cancer stage and mean pre-operative CA 19-9 serum levels (23).

CA 19-9 is a tumor marker that is frequently checked in healthy individuals when screening for various cancers including pancreatic cancer. In addition to malignancies, it is known that CA 19-9 may also increase in benign pancreatobiliary, hepatic and pulmonary diseases, thyroiditis, diabetes mellitus, and autoimmune diseases. Therefore, we should be cautious in interpreting the significance of CA 19-9 elevation (24).

The reason for CA 19-9 elevation in benign disease can be explained by several mechanisms. First of all, inflammation and proliferation of non-tumorous tissue, such as in pancreatitis, cholangitis, bronchiectasis, idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, ovarian cyst, and endometriosis, can elevate CA 19-9. CA 19-9 also increases as a result of obstructive jaundice and bronchitis as CA 19-9 excretion is blocked in these diseases. The last mechanism is when metabolic malfunction is present such as in hepatitis, diabetes mellitus, and chronic glomerulonephritis (23).

CA 19-9, or sLea glycan antigen, can be synthesized as a glycolipid (with the ceramide component incorporated into lipid bilayers of cell membranes) or as a glycoprotein (most typically O-linked to mucins). To avoid interference with antibodies and their effector system, sLea expression in normal tissues is confined to the ductal epithelium of tissues. However, it is expressed in many different types of gastrointestinal cancers, thus serving as a serum indicator of cancer. sLea molecules attached to normal cells of epithelium act as epitopes for these recognition receptors of leukocytes (endothelial E-selectin) and further aid in immunoregulation. This property is lacking in glycans expressed by malignant cells. It is well known that during malignant transformation, cell surface glycans experience considerable changes. This glycosylation alteration is a hallmark of the transition to malignancy. Malignant cells alter their glycans in a number of ways, most often by modifying their terminal chains. Overexpression of Lewis antigens, namely, sialyl Lewis x and associated antigens, has been seen in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) cell lines and tissues. These findings point to the possibility that tumor indicators, glycoproteins containing sLex, are released into the bloodstream by pancreatic tumors (25).

Hematogenous metastasis is hypothesized to be strongly related to the determinants sLea and sLex, which are involved in glycan-mediated adherence of cancer cells to vascular endothelium. Therapeutic applications for blocking this cell adhesion pathway may inhibit hematogenous metastasis. In vivo evidence supports the hypothesis that when sLe-x/a structures are overproduced in cancer cells, these facilitate the bonding of circulating cancer cells with selectins of endothelial cells, hence facilitating the emergence of metastases. E-

and P-selectins were also shown to have a substantial function in the peritoneal dissemination of pancreatic cancer cells (25).

The current study sheds light on the levels of CEA (carcinoembryonic antigen) in colorectal cancer patients vs healthy controls. Colorectal cancer patients had considerably higher mean CEA levels, with a mean SD of 150.32 ± 357.08 ng/mL, compared to healthy controls, who had a mean SD of 1.718 ± 0.69 ng/mL (as shown in Table 5 & Figure 3). With a p-value of 0.043, the observed difference was statistically significant.

CEA is a strong prognostic biomarker in patients with colorectal cancer who underwent surgical resection and adjuvant chemotherapy. Studies suggest that elevated CEA level of >5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ at the time of diagnosis of colorectal cancer is associated with poor prognosis. However, normalization of elevated CEA levels after surgery is not associated with a poor prognosis. Hence routine assessment of CEA before surgical treatment is not indicated, and usually, post-operative detection is more useful in detecting recurrence within the first year of surgery and prognosis. In colorectal cancer, serum CEA normalizes 6 weeks after the resection of the tumor. Therefore, persistently elevated CEA levels may indicate residual tumor due to incomplete resection or recurrence of the tumor (26).

Harrison et al reported that patients with node-negative colon cancer have a significant association between preoperative CEA level and survival. Patients were stratified by CEA levels of 5 ng/mL, 10 ng/mL, and 20 ng/mL, and all of the cutoffs above 5 ng/mL predicted a poor outcome. Preoperative CEA level was found to be an independent prognostic factor in patients who underwent potentially curative operations for colon and rectal cancer (24).

CEA has been reported to participate in intercellular adhesion, protection against anoikis (apoptosis associated with cell detachment from the extracellular matrix) and increased metastatic potential. Several studies reported no correlation between the grade of CEA expression in cancer tissue and the serum CEA level. However, another study reported that the grade of CEA expression in cancer tissue is related to the serum CEA level. Such inconsistent results may be attributed to methodological differences in the evaluation of the CEA expression grade in tissue. Overexpression of CEA has been reported to inhibit the cytotoxic activity of natural killer cells and lymphocytes and decrease tumor immune system activity, thereby providing a poorer outcome in patients with positive staining for CEA than those with negative staining for CEA. Hamada et al. reported that CEA localized to the basolateral membrane or stromal tissue leads to higher serum CEA levels than CEA localized to the luminal surface. This finding suggested that CEA flowing from interstitial tissue into blood vessels more strongly contributes to increased serum CEA levels than CEA flowing into the ductal lumen does. Patients with colon cancer who have lymphatic and vascular invasion in primary tumor tissue have been reported to have high serum CEA levels (27).

In this study, the mean levels of Alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) were examined between patients with hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and healthy controls. The AFP levels in the HCC patients were greater, with a mean SD of 112.39 ± 193.09 IU/mL, while the healthy controls had a mean SD of 2.70 ± 1.26 IU/mL. As seen in Table 6 and Figure 4, this difference was determined to be statistically significant (p -value = 0.007).

AFP may regulate the growth of neoplastic and normal cells by several mechanisms that include apoptotic regulation and cytoplasmic signaling modulation. Although increasing evidence suggests that AFP may regulate the growth of tumour cells, the specific mechanism for its growth-promoting activity is unclear. In HL-60 cells and HepG2 cells, AFP was shown to protect against apoptosis induced by various factors. Since tumour proliferation by AFP was found to be dependent on the cyclic AMP-protein kinase A pathway and the initiation of Ca^{2+} influx, a possible explanation could be that increases in intracellular Ca^{2+} from AFP-induced Ca^{2+} influx results in increased DNA synthesis and tumour proliferation mediated by intracellular cAMP and protease A activity. In vitro, AFP also affects the function of caspase-3 via indirect interaction with the X-linked inhibitor of the apoptosis protein, XIAP, and the cellular inhibitor of apoptosis protein, cIAP-2. As a result, AFP may play a critical role in the inhibition of the apoptotic signal transduction mediated by caspase-3.

Several studies also suggest that tumour growth results from AFP-mediated suppression of the antitumour immune response. AFP was shown to interact with macrophages and to decrease their phagocytic activity and Ia antigen expression. In addition, AFP inhibits the activity of natural killer cells, reduces proliferation of T-lymphocytes and promotes the activity of T-suppressor cells.

Detailed mechanisms regarding the upregulation of cell proliferation and tumour growth by AFP remain unknown. However, studies have shown that AFP binds to specific receptors located on the surface of normal and tumour cells, and the presence of AFP and its receptor in human placenta suggests a possible receptor-mediated mechanism for placental transport of AFP between the fetal and maternal circulations. AFP may influence the delivery of fatty acids to proliferating cells that require increased energy supply and intermediate products of β -oxidation of fatty acids. In reaction to lymphocytic blast transformation, AFP and the heptapeptide AFP14–20 might also cause a moderate stimulation of proliferation of lymphocytes and inhibition of proliferation of PHA-activated lymphocytes at concentrations of 10^7 to 10^9 M. Since the heptapeptide AFP14–20 inhibits proliferation of lymphocytes in a dose-dependent manner from patients with acute and chronic lymphocytic leukaemia with low sensitivity to anti tumour agents, AFP may be a biologically active ligand on certain human cells. AFP may have dual regulatory effects on cell proliferation and tissue growth through both stimulatory and inhibitory effects (28).

Liver cancer cells can modify their own surface antigen and change the microenvironment around the tumor lesion to implement their immune escape. Exogenous AFP can not only promote the proliferation of hepatocellular carcinoma cells and the formation of tumor blood vessels, but also enhance the anti-apoptosis effect of cancer cells. Thus, AFP plays an important role in the development and progression of liver cancer. Cellular immunity is the main immune mechanism of anticancer. Dendritic cells, natural killer cells, and T lymphocytes are involved in immune surveillance. It is confirmed that AFP could affect the three important immune cells to exert their antitumor effects (29).

In the past, many studies have attempted to understand whether or not a relationship exists between clinicopathologic features and the prognosis of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) with respect to serum alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) levels at diagnosis. One such study reviewed the clinical data of 309 pathologically proven HCC cases divided into three groups. Group 1 with normal AFP (<20 IU/mL), group 2 with moderately elevated AFP (20–399 IU/mL) and group 3 with markedly elevated AFP (\geq 400 IU/mL). Of these, there were 76 (24.6%), 78 (25.2%), and 155 patients (50.2%) in groups 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The study found that HCC patients with high AFP tended to have greater tumor size, bilobar involvement, massive or diffuse types, and portal vein thrombosis. Nonetheless, the study could not establish a correlation between increased AFP and Okuda's stages, degree of tumor differentiation, or extrahepatic metastasis (30).

Conclusion

The CA 19-9 test is a non-invasive, low-cost alternative to invasive and radiographic treatments, frequently detected in pancreatic cancer, although this alone is not adequate to make a conclusive diagnosis. Clinicians should use this test on a regular basis in patients to prevent costly and invasive treatments. CA 19-9, on the other hand, has limitations in that it can be increased in benign jaundice, pancreatitis, ovarian cancer, and other gastrointestinal cancers, limiting its use as a screening tool. The decision to initiate therapy simply based on growing CA 19-9 levels needs further evidence and should be backed by additional confirmatory testing. Similarly, CEA concentrations in non-malignant conditions might be increased, necessitating the employment of further confirmatory tests to verify the presence or absence of malignancies. CEA testing should not be utilized as a stand-alone cancer screening tool. More research is needed to determine the therapeutic consequences of CEA-based stratification for adjuvant chemotherapy and patient-specific follow-up strategies.

HCC is a complicated illness with several pathogenic pathways and risk factors, making it difficult to describe with a single biomarker. AFP (alpha-fetoprotein) remains the most often utilized biomarker in HCC treatment. Its significance in HCC has developed over time, however it is not ideal as a screening, diagnostic, and prognostic marker. There are still unanswered concerns concerning the appropriate AFP cut-off levels for HCC surveillance, diagnosis, and prognosis that need to be investigated further. The subject of how to improve AFP's effectiveness in diverse HCC scenarios by combining it with additional biomarkers such as AFP-L3 or DCP remains a hot topic. Furthermore, it is critical to determine if AFP retains its use in evaluating therapy responses

with newer drugs such as regorafenib or nivolumab. Another factor that has to be looked at is AFP's functional involvement, if any, in tumor growth.

With the advent of new and improved genomic and proteomic technologies it is now possible to develop biomarkers that are able to reliably and accurately predict cancer outcomes & response to drug therapy. While some insights are available, additional studies are required to fully comprehend the mysteries of these biomarkers.

References

1. Sinha SR, Prakash P, Singh RK, Sinha DK. Assessment of tumor markers CA 19-9, CEA, CA 125, and CA 242 for the early diagnosis and prognosis prediction of gallbladder cancer. *World J Gastrointest Surg.* 2022;14(11):1272.
2. Edoe MIA, Chutturghoon VK, Wusu-Ansah GK, Zhu H, Zhen TY, Xie HY, et al. Serum Biomarkers AFP, CEA and CA19-9 Combined Detection for Early Diagnosis of Hepatocellular Carcinoma. *Iran J Public Health.* 2019;48(2):314. A
3. Nenclares P, Harrington KJ. The biology of cancer. *Medicine.* 2020 Feb 1;48(2):67–72.
4. Malati T. Tumour markers: An overview. *Indian Journal of Clinical Biochemistry.* 2007 ;22(2):17.
5. Baj J, Bryliński Ł, Woliński F, Granat M, Kostelecka K, Duda P, et al. Biomarkers and Genetic Markers of Hepatocellular Carcinoma and Cholangiocarcinoma-What Do We Already Know. *Cancers (Basel).* 2022 ;14(6):1493–1493.
6. Ogunwobi OO, Mahmood F, Akingboye A. Biomarkers in Colorectal Cancer: Current Research and Future Prospects. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 2020;21(15):5311.
7. Chatterjee SK, Zetter BR. Cancer biomarkers: knowing the present and predicting the future. <http://dx.doi.org/101517/147966941137>. 2005 ;1(1):37–50. A
8. Luo G, Jin K, Deng S, Cheng H, Fan Z, Gong Y, et al. Roles of CA19-9 in pancreatic cancer: Biomarker, predictor and promoter. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Reviews on Cancer.* 2021;1875(2):188409.
9. Yang J, Xu R, Wang C, Qiu J, Ren B, You L. Early screening and diagnosis strategies of pancreatic cancer: a comprehensive review. *Cancer Commun.* 2021;41(12):1257–74.
10. Truty MJ, Kendrick ML, Nagorney DM, Smoot RL, Cleary SP, Graham RP, et al. Factors Predicting Response, Perioperative Outcomes, and Survival Following Total Neoadjuvant Therapy for Borderline/Locally Advanced Pancreatic Cancer. *Ann Surg.* 2021 273(2):341–9.
11. Galle PR, Foerster F, Kudo M, Chan SL, Llovet JM, Qin S, et al. Biology and significance of alpha-fetoprotein in hepatocellular carcinoma. *Liver International.* 2019;39(12):2214–29.
12. Abelev GI. Alpha-Fetoprotein in Ontogenesis and its Association with Malignant Tumors. *Adv Cancer Res.* 1971;14(C):295–358.
13. Piñero F, Dirchwolf M, Pessôa MG. Biomarkers in Hepatocellular Carcinoma: Diagnosis, Prognosis and Treatment Response Assessment. *Cells* 2020;9(6):1370. A
14. Chatterjee SK, Zetter BR. Cancer biomarkers: knowing the present and predicting the future. <http://dx.doi.org/101517/147966941137>. 2005;1(1):37–50.

15. Wang JY, Lu CY, Chu KS, Ma CJ, Wu DC, Tsai HL, et al. Prognostic Significance of Pre- and Postoperative Serum Carcinoembryonic Antigen Levels in Patients with Colorectal Cancer. *European Surgical Research*. 2007;39(4):245–50. A
16. Zhang C, Zheng W, Lv Y, Shan L, Xu D, Pan Y, et al. Postoperative carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) levels predict outcomes after resection of colorectal cancer in patients with normal preoperative CEA levels. *Transl Cancer Res*. 2020;9(1):111.
17. Duffy MJ. Carcinoembryonic Antigen as a Marker for Colorectal Cancer: Is It Clinically Useful? *Clin Chem*. 2001;47(4):624–30.
18. Herlyn M, Steplewski Z, Herlyn D, Koprowski H. Colorectal carcinoma-specific antigen: detection by means of monoclonal antibodies. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 1979;76(3):1438–42.
19. Hernando JJ, Von Kleist S, Grunert F. A repertoire of monoclonal antibodies reveals extensive epitope heterogeneity in CEA purified from neoplasms originating from different organs. *Int J Cancer*. 1994;56(5):655–61.
20. Glick PL, Pohlson EC, Resta R, Payne C, Mosbarger H, Luthy DA, et al. Maternal serum alpha-fetoprotein is a marker for fetal anomalies in pediatric surgery. *J Pediatr Surg*. 1988;23(1):16–20.
21. Wu L, Huang P, Wang F, Li D, Xie E, Zhang Y, et al. Relationship between serum CA19-9 and CEA levels and prognosis of pancreatic cancer. *Ann Transl Med [Internet]*. 2015 Dec 1 [cited 2024 Jan 13];3(21):328.
22. Lee CW, Tsai HI, Lee WC, Huang SW, Lin CY, Hsieh YC, et al. Normal Alpha-Fetoprotein Hepatocellular Carcinoma: Are They Really Normal? *J Clin Med*. 2019;8(10):1736.
23. Ballehaninna UK, Chamberlain RS. Serum CA 19-9 as a Biomarker for Pancreatic Cancer-A Comprehensive Review. *Indian J Surg Oncol*. 2011;2(2):88–100. A
24. Kim S, Park BK, Seo JH, Choi J, Choi JW, Lee CK, et al. Carbohydrate antigen 19-9 elevation without evidence of malignant or pancreatobiliary diseases. *Scientific Reports* 2020 10:1. 2020;10(1):1–9.
25. Sai L, Janga N, Sambe HG, Yasir M, Man RK, Gogikar A, et al. Holistic Understanding of the Role of Carbohydrate Antigen 19-9 in Pancreatic Cancer Screening, Early Diagnosis, and Prognosis: A Systematic Review. 2023;
26. Bhatti I, Patel M, Dennison AR, Thomas MW, Garcea G. Utility of postoperative CEA for surveillance of recurrence after resection of primary colorectal cancer. *International Journal of Surgery*. 2015 Apr 1;16(Part A):123–8.
27. Saito G, Sadahiro S, Okada K, Tanaka A, Suzuki T, Kamijo A. Relation between Carcinoembryonic Antigen Levels in Colon Cancer Tissue and Serum Carcinoembryonic Antigen Levels at Initial Surgery and Recurrence. *Oncology*. 2016;91(2):85–9.
28. Galle PR, Foerster F, Kudo M, Chan SL, Llovet JM, Qin S, et al. Biology and significance of alpha-fetoprotein in hepatocellular carcinoma. *Liver International*. 2019;39(12):2214–29
29. Wang X, Wang Q. Alpha-fetoprotein and hepatocellular carcinoma immunity. *Can J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2018;2018.
30. Luo JC, Hwang SJ, Wu JC, Lai CR, Li CP, Chang FY, et al. Clinical characteristics and prognosis of hepatocellular carcinoma patients with paraneoplastic syndromes. *Hepatogastroenterology*. 2002;49(47):1315–9.